

Cyclohexenone Derivatives. Part IV'. Evidence of C₁-Alkylation of Hagemann's Ester*

D. Nasipuri, G. Sarkar, R. Roy, and (in part) M. Guha

A crystalline compound, *m.p.* 172°, has been isolated during mono-alkylation of Hagemann's ester with ethyl β -halopropionate. It is identified as ethyl 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10-octahydro-2,7-dioxonaphthalene-10-carboxylate, presumably formed as a result of C₁-alkylation of Hagemann's ester, followed by an internal Claisen condensation. C₁-Alkylation is also evidenced in the isopropylation of Hagemann's ester where the 1-isopropyl derivative actually has been isolated and its structure confirmed by synthesis.

Since its original preparation¹, Hagemann's ester (ethyl 2-methyl-4-oxocyclohex-2-enyl-1-carboxylate) (I) has been extensively used as intermediate for various syntheses²⁻⁷. As a vinylogous β oxo-ester, it forms a mesomeric anion under the influence of a base and is capable of directing its nucleophilic attack from several points, C₁ and C₃ in particular. Uptil now, the consensus of all published data is that alkylation of Hagemann's ester leads exclusively to C₃-alkylated product, although subsequent alkylation⁴ involves both C₁ and C₃. Evidence in support of this came mainly from the hydrolysis of the alkylated products and identification of the resultant cyclohexenones, either by oxidative degradation⁵ or by unambiguous synthesis⁶. In the present communication are recorded some of the present authors' observations which do not fully accord with this view, but show that along with C₃-alkylation, there is a substantial amount ($\sim 25\%$) of C₁-alkylation of Hagemann's ester in some cases.

In connection with some other experiments in our laboratory¹, an authentic specimen of β 2-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionic acid was required. This acid has been prepared by at least four different groups of workers⁷ by alkylation of Hagemann's ester with ethyl β -halopropionate and hydrolysis of the resultant keto ester (II). No byproduct in this reaction has been reported. Surprisingly, during alkylation of Hagemann's ester

* Presented at the Joint Convention of the Indian Chemical Society and the Chemical Research Committee of the C.S.I.R., held at Aligarh, in December, 1965.

1. Part III, Nasipuri and Guha, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 243.

2. Hagemann, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 876.

3. (a) Cornubert and Maurel, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1931, 49, 1516; (b) Bergmann and Weismann, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1930, 4, 266; (c) Smith and Renault, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 631; (d) Hogg, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 161; (e) Horning *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 1771; (f) Stork and Burgstahler, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 3544; Ghatak *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1955, 3145; Marshall and Cohen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2773.

4. (a) Mukherji, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 99; (b) Dyer *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4778.

5. (a) Kots and Anger, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 446; Rabe and Pollock, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2924; (b) Diekmann, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2697; (c) Kots *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1913, 400, 72.

6. Edgar *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1063.

7. (a) Nentzeosu and Cioranescu, *Ber.*, 1942, 75, 1785; (b) Schwenk and Block, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 3050; (c) Inhoffen and Frinz, *Chem. Ber.*, 1954, 87, 984; (d) Adlerova *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1958, 23, 681; Buchta and Ungomach, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 1552.

by the present workers with ethyl β -bromo-(chloro-) propionate or ethyl acrylate in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide, along with the expected liquid keto-ester(II) quite a substantial amount (15-20%) of a solid was obtained. The yield of the solid was subsequently increased to 25-30% by the use of an excess of base (1.5 mole). In view of this compound not being mentioned in the earlier literature, we thought it to be of interest to investigate its structure and explain its formation from Hagemann's ester under the reaction condition.

(I): R = H.

(II): R = CH₂CH₂CO₂Et.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII): R' = CO₂Et.

(VIII): R' = R = H.

(IX)

The compound is a pale yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 172°, b.p. 195-200°/0.5 mm. It is slightly soluble in water but readily so in aqueous sodium bicarbonate from which it is regenerated by addition of mineral acids. It was separated from the alkylated product by cooling the total distillate in a refrigerator overnight and filtering the crystalline solid from the liquid by means of a little light petroleum. It could also be extracted from the crude reaction mixture by aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The molecular weight (236; mass spectroscopy), and elemental analysis of the compound correspond to a formula C₁₃H₁₆O₄, derivable from the neutral keto-ester (II) through elimination of one molecule of ethanol. This together with its UV and IR absorption data: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 325 m μ (log ϵ , 4.37) and 394 m μ (log ϵ , 4.14), λ_{max} (in ethanolic sodium ethoxide) 394 m μ (log ϵ , 5.24); ν (KBr pellet) $\sim$ 2600 (-OH)^{*}, 1718 (-CO₂Et), 1615 (-C=O), and 1580 cm⁻¹ (C=C), indicate a diketone-ester structure (such as III) existing in the hydrogen-bonded enolic form in the solid state (as IV:R=H). NMR and IR spectra in deuteriochloroform and chloroform, respectively, on the other hand, are broadly consistent with a mixture of keto and enol forms. Such a structure (III) might conceivably be formed by an intramolecular Claisen condensation of the alkylated Hagemann's ester (II).

^{*}The usual hydroxy band at 3400-3200 cm⁻¹ is shifted to about 2600 cm⁻¹ due to formation of strong H-bonds⁸.

⁸S. Makiishi, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco and Nankaido Company Ltd., Tokyo, 1962, p. 60.

That the above structural assignment was incorrect became soon apparent from the following two observations. Firstly, the neutral keto-ester (II) could not be cyclised to the diketone (III) under the condition of alkylation reaction. Secondly, when the crystalline byproduct, m.p. 172°, was submitted to hydrolytic decarboxylation, an acidic diketone (vinylogous), m.p. 177°, was obtained, having $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 318 μ (log ϵ , 4.40) and λ_{max} (in dilute alkali) 382 μ (log ϵ , 4.92), which was clearly different from 1,2,3,4,5,8,7,8-octahydro-1,6-dioxonaphthalene⁹, m.p. 44-46°, expected from structure (III), but was identical with the enolic form of isomeric 2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10-octahydro-2,7-dioxonaphthalene (VIII), m.p. 174-76°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 321 μ (log ϵ , 4.25), recently synthesised¹⁰. It afforded a monomethyl ether, m.p. 08° (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 04-95°) and an *N*-methylanilido derivative, m.p. 170°. The NMR spectrum of the methyl ether showed two vinyl protons at 4.28 and 4.58 τ in agreement with the structure. On the basis of this finding, the only other structure, consistent with the physical and chemical properties of the compound, is the diketo-ester (VI) and its tautomeric enol form (VII; R=H), with an angular ethoxy-carbonyl group. Its formation could be explained by an initial alkylation of Hagemann's ester at C₁ to yield the keto-ester (V: R = CH₂CH₂CO₂Et) which subsequently underwent the Claisen condensation in presence of a base involving the vinylogously reactive methyl group. Physical properties, such as acidity and the UV absorption data, seemed to be in better fitting with this structure (VII: R=H).

Final confirmation of the structure came from NMR data of the methyl ether (VII: R=Me) which was obtained as a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 107°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 310 μ (log ϵ , 4.48)^{10b} by treatment of the keto-ester (VI) with diazomethane. The proton resonance spectrum^a, triplet (3) at 8.78 τ and a quartet (2) at 5.82 τ ($J=7$ cps) (CO₂CH₂CH₃), broad multiplet (8) at 8.3-7.4 τ (methylene protons), sharp singlet (3) at 6.45 τ (OMe), two singlets (1+1) at 4.50 and 4.10 τ (vinyl protons), fitted nicely to structure (VII: R=Me) but not to the alternative structure (IV: R=Me), possessing only one vinyl proton.

The isolation of the diketo-ester (VI) indicates that the alkylation of Hagemann's ester is not as selective as formerly believed, but it leads, at least in some cases, to a mixture of C₂- and C₁-alkylated products, the former predominating. In the light of this present finding, some of the experimental data of Adlerova *et al.*^{7d} can be rationalised. These workers alkylated Hagemann's ester with ethyl bromoacetate and β -bromopropionate and hydrolysed the products to substituted cyclohexenyl-acetic and -propionic acid, respectively, in approximately 40% yield, but on crystallisation, the yields of these acids dropped to 7%, possibly due to presence of isomeric acids in the mixture owing to C₁-alkylation. Surprisingly enough, in so many cases of alkylation of Hagemann's ester, no doubt arose as to the purity of the products, though some of these experiments were construed as direct evidence for C₂-alkylation. One possible explanation is that the C₁-substituted ester is more resistant to hydrolysis and is therefore left out in the higher-boiling fractions during such operations. All structural determinations in the past were based on the reactions of the hydrolysed products. The ease of hydrolysis of the quaternary ethoxycarbonyl group in the vinylogous diketo-ester (VI), which is similarly substituted, is possibly due to participation of the enolate ion.

^aThe spectrum was taken in deuteriochloroform solution with tetraethylsilane as internal indicator on a 60 Mc machine. Figures in parentheses denote the number of protons.

9. Birch *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 782.

10. (a) Marshall and Andersen, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 30, 1292; (b) M. Kocor, private communication.

To investigate this point further, Hagemann's ester was alkylated with isopropyl iodide²⁰ in presence of a base; the alkylated product afforded two semicarbazones, one having m.p. 141.5° (major) and the other, m.p. 210°. Hydrolysis of the mixed keto-esters furnished 2-isopropyl-3-methylcyclohex-2-en-1-one²⁶ and some residual keto-ester (≈ 15%) in the higher-boiling fraction. The latter readily formed a semicarbazone, m.p. 210°, identical as above, and a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 145°, and was found to be identical with ethyl 1-isopropyl-2-methyl-4-oxocyclohex-2-enyl-1-carboxylate (V: R=CHMe₂), an authentic specimen of which was synthesised as follows.

Ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-2-isopropyl 5-cyclohexanoate, prepared by Michael addition of methyl vinyl ketone and ethyl isopropylmalonate, was submitted to an internal aldol condensation to yield ethyl 1-isopropyl-2,4-dioxocyclohexyl-1-carboxylate (IX) in rather poor yield. The latter was converted into its 4-isobutyl enol ether* and treated successively with methylmagnesium iodide and dilute acid¹² to afford the keto-ester (V: R=CHMe₂). Identity of the two keto-esters was established through comparison of their semicarbazones and dinitrophenylhydrazones.

TLC of the isopropylated product also indicated two major components. NMR spectrum showed it to be a mixture (30:70 as a rough approximation) of C₂- and C₃-substituted Hagemann's ester, the ratio being determined by the relative area of the vinyl proton (singlet) at C₂ and the allylic proton (triplet) at C₁, which were distinctly seen in the spectrum. A quantitative treatment of a number of alkylated Hagemann's ester, based on NMR spectra, will be reported in a future communication.

One thing, however, still remains obscure to us. Neither the keto-ester (II) nor its de ethoxycarbonylated product underwent intramolecular Claisen condensation with base (sodium ethoxide in ethanol or potassium *t*-amylate in dry benzene), whereas the isomeric keto-ester (V: R=CH₂CH₂CO₂Et) seemed to undergo ready cyclisation. This differential behaviour of the two keto-esters is hardly understood since the same vinylogously reactive methyl group is present in both the molecules. The quaternary ethoxycarbonyl group in the latter (V) has possibly something to do with the ring-closure. We are currently engaged in synthesising a few keto-esters of type (V) in order to find some explanation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hagemann's Ester (I).—Hagemann's ester was prepared according to the procedure of Smith and Rozauk²⁰. A redistilled material, b.p. 120°/2mm. n_D^{25} 1.4815 (semicarbazone m.p. 165°) was used for all alkylation reactions.

Alkylation of Hagemann's Ester with Ethyl β -Chloro- and β -Bromo-propionates

Formation of Ethyl 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10-Octahydro-2,7-dioxonaphthalene-1C-carboxylate (VII: R=H): (a). *With One Mole of Base*.—The procedure employed was essentially similar to that of Schwenk and Bloch^{7b} or of Edgar *et al.*⁶. In a typical experiment, Hage-

* The structure of the enol ether was based on previous analogy¹¹.

11. Courty, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3046; Pyne *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 85, 199; Bannerji, *ibid.*, 1962, 84, 765.

12. Frank and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1645.

mann's ester (0.066*M*, 12.1 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.060*M*, 1.54 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (55 ml), followed by ethyl β -chloropropionate (0.003*M*, 9.1 g.) (or equivalent amount of β -bromopropionate). The mixture was gently refluxed for 4-6 hr. on a steam bath. Most of the ethanol was removed at the water pump, the residue treated with cold dilute acid, and the organic matter thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated. The residue on cooling in a refrigerator overnight deposited some solid which was transferred to a Buchner funnel and washed free of the adherent liquid with a mixture of benzene and light petroleum. Alternatively, the residue on evaporation of the ether was distilled in vacuum and after rejection of a little forerun, the following fractions were collected:

Fraction.	Amount.	D.P.
A	3.5 g.	150-80°/0.4 mm.
B	3.6	160-85°/0.4
C	4.4	185-200°/0.4

Fractions B and C on keeping in the refrigerator deposited some solid which was collected and washed with solvent as before. The crude solid, m.p. 150-80°, in each case was crystallised from ethyl acetate (or benzene-petroleum) to afford pale yellow needles, m.p. 168-70° (2.31-3.12 g., 15-20%). After several crystallisations, it was obtained in light yellow prisms, m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 66.0, 65.3; H, 7.35, 6.80. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.10; H, 6.80%). Molecular weight, as determined by mass spectroscopy, was found to be 236. The compound developed a greenish violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and could be titrated with NaOH, using phenolphthalein as indicator. It had an equivalent weight of 236 in agreement with the molecular formula. In one of the experiments, the yield was calculated by alkali titration of the total distillate and was found to be 21%.

Fraction A in the above experiment and the filtrate after separation of the solid consisted mostly of the neutral keto-ester (II), contaminated possibly with a little of 1-alkylated product. This was hydrolysed to afford β -2-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionic acid as a gum which was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in white plates, m.p. 77-78°.

(b). *With an Excess of Base.*—A mixture of Hagemann's ester (0.1*M*, 18.2 g.), ethyl β -chloropropionate (0.1*M*, 13.65 g.), and ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.15 *M*, 3.45 g.) and ethanol (60 ml), was heated under reflux for 4 hr. and the product worked up as in experiment (a). The ethereal extract was repeatedly extracted with cold 10% sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline extract was cooled and acidified carefully with HCl (conc.). The heavy oil separating was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The viscous residue on being seeded with a crystal of the diketo-ester (VI) from a previous sample set to a solid mass (8.4 g.). This was once crystallised from benzene-petroleum to yield the almost pure *diketo-ester* (VI) (6.8 g., 30%), m.p. 165-71°. The neutral material left in the ethereal layer in the previous operation was dried (Na_2SO_4) and distilled *in vacuo*. After a little forerun, it afforded the keto-ester (II) as an oil, b.p. 160-65°/2 mm, yield 14.5 g. (56%). It was hydrolysed with refluxing 42% hydriodic acid^{7b} to furnish β -2-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionic acid

(yield, 58%) in an almost pure state. One crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum afforded white crystals, m.p. 77-78° (36%). This was further characterised through the formation of a semicarbazone, m.p. 223°. (Found: C, 55.0; H, 6.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{17}O_3N_3$: C, 55.2; H, 7.1%).

Alkylation of Hagemann's Ester with Ethyl Acrylate

To a cooled solution of Hagemann's ester (0.1M, 18.2 g.) and ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (2.3 g.) and ethanol (40 ml), was added ethyl acrylate (10.0 g.) slowly and with constant shaking. The mixture was then gently refluxed for 3 hr. on a water bath. The product was worked up in the usual way. The diketo-ester (VI), m.p. 164-70° (3.3g., 15%) was isolated from the reaction mixture.

Ethyl 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10-Hexahydro-2-oxo-7-methylzaphthalene-10-carboxylate (VII: R = Me).—A solution of the diketo-ester (VI) (3.5 g.) in methanol was slowly added to an excess of ethereal solution of diazomethane. On completion of the reaction, the solution was diluted with water; the ether layer was separated, washed with aqueous NaOH, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The residue solidified to a yellow mass which was crystallised from benzene-methanol in deep yellow prisms, m.p. 107°. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 7.5. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2%).

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10-Octahydro-2, 7-dioxonaphthalene (VIII).—The diketo-ester (VI) (1g.) was heated under reflux with a solution of KOH (1 g.) in water (10 ml) for 3 hr. The red solution was cooled, acidified with $N-H_2SO_4$, and boiled for further 30 min. to effect complete decarboxylation. The solution on cooling deposited the diketone (VIII) as a crystalline solid (0.7g.). This was collected by filtration and crystallised several times from dilute acetic acid to furnish pale yellow plates, m.p. 177°. (Found: C, 72.9; H, 7.4; equiv., 167. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{12}O_2$: C, 73.1; H, 7.3%; equiv., 168).

2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10-Hexahydro-2-oxo-7-methylzaphthalene: *Methyl Ether of the Diketone* (VIII).—A mixture of the above diketone (13.8 g.), methanol (7.5 ml), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.), and dry benzene (60 ml) was refluxed in an oil bath until the water was completely separated. The mixture was neutralised with a little ethanolic sodium ethoxide and then poured on water. The benzene layer was separated, washed with a solution of 4% cold aqueous NaOH, dried, and the solvent removed. The residual solid, m.p. 83-89° (8.0 g.), was distilled at 162-65°/8mm and finally crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in yellow needles, m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 7.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O$: C, 74.2; H, 7.9%). The NMR showed two singlets (very finely split) (1+1 H) at 4.28 and 4.58 τ (vinyl protons), a sharp singlet (3 H) at 6.30 τ (OMe), and irregular multiplets at 7.3-8.5 τ (methylene protons).

N-Methylanilido Derivative.—The diketone (VIII) (1.64 g.), *N*-methylaniline (1.07 g.), and dry benzene (30 ml) were heated under reflux for 30 hr. The cooled mixture was poured over ice and extracted with ether. The red solid after evaporation of the ether was absorbed on activated alumina and eluted with benzene. The *N-methylanilido*, thus obtained, was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in yellow crystals, m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 80.6; H, 7.7; N, 5.9. $C_{17}H_{19}ON$ requires C, 80.6; H, 7.5; N, 5.5%); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 366 μ (log ϵ , 3.48).

Alkylation of Hagemann's Ester with Isopropyl Iodide

(a). *With Sodium Ethoxide*.—A solution of Hagemann's ester (0.15M, 27.2 g.), ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (3.5 g.) and ethanol (60 ml), and an excess of isopropyl iodide, was refluxed on a water bath for 16 hr. The product was worked up in the usual manner and on distillation afforded isopropylated Hagemann's ester, b.p. 125-30°/2 mm (22.5 g., 87%).

(b). *With Potassium t-Butylate*.—Hagemann's ester (60 g.) was isopropylated in presence of potassium *t*-butylate, prepared from potassium (14 g.) and *t*-butanol (280 ml) by refluxing the mixture with an excess of isopropyl iodide on a water bath for 16 hr. The alkylated product afforded a colorless oil, b.p. 128-30°/2mm (57 g., 76%). The product was almost identical with that in experiment (a) as proved by subsequent reactions, and consisted of approximately 30% C₁-isopropylated and 70% C₃-isopropylated Hagemann's esters.

Semicarbazones.—The above ester on treatment with a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate in the usual way afforded as a first crop a semicarbazone which was crystallised from ethanol in white plates, m.p. 210°. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 8.3; N, 14.4. C₁₂H₁₅O₃N₃ requires C, 59.8; H, 8.3; N, 14.9%). The mother liquor on keeping overnight at a warm temperature afforded another semicarbazone which solidified only on cooling. It was crystallised several times from ethanol and finally obtained as a colorless amorphous powder, m.p. 141.5°. (Found: C, 55.9; H, 8.2; N, 13.7%). The mixed m.p. with the other sample was considerably depressed. The yields of the semicarbazones were approximately in the ratio of 1:3.

Hydrolysis of the Isopropylated Hagemann's Ester.—The foregoing mixture of 1- and 3-isopropylated Hagemann's esters from experiment (b) (57g.) was heated under reflux with 15% EtOH-KOH (125 ml) for 8 hr. Most of the solvent was distilled and the residue diluted with sufficient ice-water. On being acidified with HCl(dil.), the mixture was heated at 80° for 1 hr. to complete decarboxylation. The product was isolated with ether and carefully distilled in vacuum, using an efficient fractionating column. *First fraction* was a sweet-smelling, colorless oil, b.p. 105-10°/4mm (21.2 g., 54%), consisting mostly of 2-isopropyl-3-methylcyclohex-2-en-1-one. The latter was characterised through its semicarbazone, m.p. 108-89°, and a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 178° (from benzene-methanol). (Found: C, 57.6; H, 0.2; N, 16.3. C₁₆H₂₀O₄N₄ requires C, 57.8; H, 0.0; N, 16.5%).

The *second fraction*, b.p. 145-50°/4mm (8.1 g., ~ 15%) was also an oil, found to be identical with *ethyl 1-isopropyl-2-methyl-4-oxocyclohex-2-enyl-1-carboxylate* (V: R=*i*-Pr) (*vide infra*). (Found: C, 70.1; H, 9.3. C₁₈H₂₀O₃ requires C, 69.6; H, 8.9%). It furnished readily a *semicarbazone* which was crystallised several times from ethanol in white prisms, m.p. 210°. (Found: C, 60.3; H, 8.6; N, 14.5. C₁₄H₁₈O₃N₃ requires C, 59.8; H, 8.3; N, 14.9%). The *dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from benzene-ethanol in red needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 55.9; H, 6.2; N, 13.7. C₁₆H₂₄O₆N₄ requires C, 56.4; H, 5.9; N, 13.9%).

Ethyl 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-isopropyl-5-oxohexanoate.—A mixture of methyl vinyl ketone (3.5 g.) and ethyl isopropylmalonate (10.3 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was treated with a few drops of ethanolic sodium ethoxide. Much heat was evolved and the reaction was completed by heating for 1 hr. more. The product was worked up in the usual way and

distillation afforded *ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-2-isopropyl-5-oxohexanoate* as a colorless oil, b.p. 150-55°/4mm (8.5 g.). (Found: C, 62.2; H, 9.2. $C_{14}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 61.8; H, 8.8%).

Ethyl 1-Isopropyl-2,4-dioxocyclohexyl-1-carboxylate (IX).—The above keto-diester (8.5 g.) was cyclized by heating with a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.8 g.) and ethanol (40 ml), for 20 hr. on a water bath. Most of the ethanol was then removed in the water pump; the residue was cooled and diluted with water. The neutral matter was removed by extraction with ether and the alkaline solution acidified. The heavy oil separating was taken up in ether, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent removed to furnish a viscous oil (8 g.) which was used in the next operation.

Isobutyl Ether of the Diketo-ester (IX).—The above crude diketo-ester (8 g.), isobutanol (8 ml), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.), and dry benzene (25 ml) were refluxed in an oil bath for 14 hr., using a Stark-Dean water separator. The mixture was cooled, neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, and then worked up in the usual way. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was distilled *in vacuo*, using an efficient fractionating column. The fraction boiling at 140-45°/0.4mm was collected. (2 g.). (Found: C, 68.5; H, 9.7. $C_{16}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 68.1; H, 9.2%).

Ethyl 1-Isopropyl 2-methyl-4-oxocyclohex-2-enyl-1-carboxylate (V: R=i-Pr).—To a solution of the above enol ether (2 g.) in ether (5 ml) was added dropwise a solution of MgI_2 , prepared from Mg (0.2 g.), MeI (1 ml), and ether (10 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr., cooled, and then decomposed with $2N-H_2SO_4$. The product was worked up in the usual way and finally distilled to afford an oil (0.5 g.), b.p. 125-30°/0.4mm. Half of this was converted into a semicarbazone which after several crystallisations from methanol furnished an amorphous, white powder, m.p. 210°. (Found: C, 59.9; H, 8.1; N, 14.8. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{23}O_3N_3$: C, 59.8; H, 8.3; N, 14.9%). The other half was converted into a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 145° (from benzene-ethanol). (Found: C, 56.6; H, 6.0; N, 14.3. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_6N_4$: C, 56.4; H, 5.9; N, 13.9%). The mixed m.p.s of the semicarbazone and the dinitrophenylhydrazone with those from alkylated product of Hagemann's ester remained undepressed.

Partial support of this work by the University Grants Commission and by the donation of E.I.P.W. of Calcutta is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are due to Professor M. Kocor for supplying information regarding ketone (VIII) prior to publication, to Dr. B. Das for determination of molecular weight, and Mr. R. N. Chakravarty for microanalysis.